

Giorgio Bassani's notes between tradition and innovation

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Despite being considered a minimal and 'parasitic' text, because they nestle in the edges of the page, writer's annotations to the books of his library are a critically important source (Del Vento 2019), because they allow us to reconstruct his history, tastes, and poetics. Being a text that originates from another text to explain, comment on or correct it, the note is also a complex textual form, difficult to manage and edit exhaustively (Milone 2022). It poses three main critical issues:

1. *Representation*. The task is to correctly represent the link between note and text in the edition: this operation is difficult and unclear with the tools of traditional philology because it requires the use of a complex system of symbols that may confuse the reader (McGann 2001).
2. *Classification*. Alongside the verbal notes, there are the "non-verbal" ones (underlining, sidebars, asterisks): an elusive and rich category that the edition merely partially records, with a significant loss of information (Shillingsburg 2015).
3. *Systematisation*. The single note has multiple relationships with the contiguous ones, with those in other books, with the writer's manuscripts. Thus, we need to systematise the data to derive statistics and information towards the reconstruction of the author's method of annotation (Martinelli 2017).

Sempronio è cresciuto in un altro ambiente ancora; le asprezze della vita lo hanno convinto che il mondo degli uomini non è che una giostra di egoismi in lotta, che la bontà, la generosità, il disinteresse sono invenzioni ipocrite, che l'unica legge valida è quella per cui i forti trionfano dei deboli; e quindi si comporta in conseguenza, cercando in tutti i modi di attuare il trionfo della sua forza. [p. 98, rr. 3-10] (L)

ma la nostra è | in gran parte | l'epoca delle | tirannie
irrespon|sabili, al di là | della psicologia e | della
volontà.

Figure 1 - Bassani's annotation and the editorial text

These issues clearly emerged in the edition of the library of Giorgio Bassani (1916-2000), one of the most important Italian writers of the 20th century, suggesting the possibility of verifying whether, and in what terms, the digital environment could obviate them, thanks to its properties: the reticular and hypertextual nature, the need for formalisation, the possibility of associating the facsimile of the annotated page with the transcription of the notes. We have therefore chosen to test a dual mode of edition, setting alongside the traditional (printed) edition of the notes a prototype of a digital edition (modelled on Bassani's notes to *La scuola dell'uomo* by Guido Calogero), which reproduces and adapts the editorial criteria of the traditional edition (Siciliano / Del Grosso 2022). So, we will better pursue the objectives typical of the study of an author's library: identification of Bassani's working method; recurring patterns in the annotation; what kind of reader Bassani is; studying all the "non-verbal" annotations which are often overlooked.

The model is based on an innovative use of the XML/TEI ¹ schema, ² stemming from the reflection on the nature of the note: ³ it is conceptually more important to the philologist than the text to which it refers. This principle is not matched by a specific editorial solution in the TEI vocabulary (Estill 2016), which rather suggests treating the authorial notes as if they were an appendix to the main text, within which they are generally transcribed in the encoding with the tags <note> and <label>. Our model reverses this hierarchy (as discussed also by Boot 2009) by giving greater importance to the notes. Considered as individual units with their own autonomy and value, they are first encoded on the metadata level (<TeiHeader>) as <msItem> in <msDesc> (adopting the method for collections of manuscript contents), ⁴ and then in the section that houses the transcription of the main text (<text>) they are transcribed as <div>, separating them from the printed text, transcribed in a subordinate position.

The multi-dimensional, multi-modal and hierarchical digital representation of a textual object suggested by TEI is also well suited to the composite and structured textuality of the note, with a better rendering in terms of accuracy and completeness of information. This is the case of the formalisation of the relationship between the note and the printed text, which can be clearly expressed by describing in <sourceDoc> the annotated page as a surface (<surface>) consisting of several areas (<zone>), using the *embedded-transcription* method proposed by the module 11 of the TEI guidelines. ⁵ The elasticity and hierarchical structure of the taxonomies inscribed in the document with the <taxonomy> tag, in the section dedicated to the description of the encoding metadata (<classDecl>), then allows for the representation of all types of annotation, ⁶ including non-verbal ones, encoded as <msI-

tem> in the <msDesc>, like the verbal ones, and as <metamark> in <sourceDoc>. Everything that has been encoded is indexable, and numerous increasingly complex and refined queries can then be carried out, cross-referencing different parameters (type, theme, position, tool with which the note is written).

Our proposal, based on hybrid approach to the author's note, has revealed the fruitful exchange between the traditional philological method and the digital one. In fact, the hierarchical language of the TEI allows the work of formal and critical analysis carried out by the philologist, which remains preliminary and essential, to be translated into the digital environment, enhancing it through a clearer, more ordered, and richer representation.

Finally, a web application prototype based on eXistDB ⁷ technology is under development for the publication and exploitation of the digital edition. At current stage the applet, developed within a thesis project, ⁸ allows scholars to search among the encoded notes with advanced searching capabilities (for example, fuzzy matching and proximity matching), to better study Bassani's thoughts.

Figure 2 - The ongoing digital archive

Notes

1. <https://tei-c.org/guidelines/>
2. Many similar projects are devoted to author's *marginalia*, like *Beckett digital library* (<https://www.beckettarchive.org/library/home/welcome>), *Melville's Marginalia* (<https://melvilles-marginalia.org/>) and *Mill Marginalia Online* (<https://blog.mill-marginalia.org/>), even if they choose different TEI encoding approaches. For *Mill Marginalia Online* see also Pionke (2020).

3. We choose the TEI expressivity which enables to link the different elements of the edition producing not only hierarchical data, but also graph-like ones. Moreover, Linked Open Data method can be taken into account in further development exploiting, for example, the Web Annotation Data Model. This latter model is already defined within the TEI standoff approach to encode annotations.

4. <https://tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/MS.html>

5. <https://tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/PH.html>

6. The annotations are labeled with various classes of different taxonomies. This gives us the possibility to explicitly establish the conceptual relationship between the annotations and the corresponding printed-text.

7. <http://exist-db.org/exist/apps/homepage/index.html>

8. We thanks Vanessa Bianconi for her precious work carried out for her thesis in Digital Humanities at University of Pisa.

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